

ARE mGPS, SIS, AND LCS SIGNIFICANT IN PREDICTING FIRST-LINE PALLIATIVE CHEMOTHERAPY RESPONSE AND PROGNOSIS IN PATIENTS WITH METASTATIC GASTRIC CANCER?

Keywords

Metastatic gastric cancer,

Glasgow Prognostic Score,

Systemic Inflammation Score,

Lymphocyte C-reactive protein Score

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to assess the prognostic value of the modified Glasgow Prognostic Score (mGPS), systemic inflammation score (SIS), and “lymphocyte C-reactive protein score” (LCS) in metastatic gastric cancer (GC) patients who received first-line palliative chemotherapy. A total of 97 GC patients were enrolled in this retrospective study. The mGPS is defined based on the combination of serum CRP and Albumin (Alb) levels. The lymphocyte-monocyte ratio (LMR) was calculated as the circulating lymphocyte count divided by the circulating monocyte count. Dichotomous variables of Alb and LMR formulate the SIS. No significant differences were observed between groups in progression-free survival (PFS) or overall survival (OS) across mGPS, SIS, and LCS scores. When patients were divided into two groups—those who underwent surgery and those who did not—the group without surgery had significantly worse PFS (3.73 months) in patients with an mGPS score of 2 ($p=0.034$). Still, there was no significant difference in OS ($p=0.44$). Patients with SIS scores of 0 or 1 were grouped and compared for survival with those with a score of 2. As a result of these evaluations, in patients without surgery, the SIS score 2 group had a PFS of 5.30 months, while the SIS score 0-1 group had a PFS of 7.34 months, and similarly, the SIS score 2 group had an OS of 13.30 months and the SIS score 0-1 group had an OS of 15.60 months, indicating worse survival times. In this study, LCS and SIS were investigated for the first time in patients with metastatic gastric cancer. The retrospective nature of our study and the relatively small number of patients (particularly in subgroup analyses) may be considered limitations. However, the scarcity of literature on this topic at the metastatic stage indicates that our study provides important information and that further, larger-scale research is needed in this area.

INTRODUCTION

Gastric cancer (GC) is the fifth most prevalent malignancy around the world, ranking sixth in tumor mortality.¹ Palliative chemotherapy for advanced or metastatic disease can improve survival and quality of life in patients with GC.² Even though great efforts have been made in developing advanced therapeutic regimens for this disease recently, the prognosis and survival of GC patients remain severe, and their 5-year survival rate was ~30% in advanced cancer patients.²

To identify high-risk patients, predict prognosis, and improve survival, it is necessary to explore clinically feasible parameters. A growing body of evidence demonstrates that patient outcomes in cancer are determined not only by tumor-related factors but also by host-related factors, particularly the systemic inflammatory response.^{3,4} Several recent studies have revealed a correlation between clinical outcomes with common solid tumors (colorectal cancer, lung cancer, breast cancer, and pancreatic cancer, etc.) and systemic inflammatory response, including plasma C-reactive protein (CRP), hypoalbuminemia, and a selective combination of C-reactive protein and albumin termed as Glasgow Prognostic Score (GPS).^{5,6}

Given the limited number of studies in this field, both globally and in our country, this study aimed to evaluate the prognostic role of the modified Glasgow Prognostic Score (mGPS), systemic inflammation score (SIS), and lymphocyte C-reactive protein score (LCS) in metastatic gastric cancer patients receiving first-line palliative chemotherapy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study examined cases of gastric carcinoma recorded in the archives of the Medical Oncology

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Department, Faculty of Medicine, Afyonkarahisar Health Sciences University, between January 1, 2011, and December 31, 2022. Cases for which pathology reports or radiological, laboratory, and survival data were unavailable were excluded. A total of 97 GC patients who received at least two cycles of first-line palliative chemotherapy were enrolled in this retrospective study (consort diagram, figure 1).

Figure 1. Consort diagram

The patients’ hematological and laboratory parameters were recorded. These included lymphocyte and monocyte counts, serum Albumin (Alb), and CRP levels. The mGPS is defined based on the combination of serum CRP and Alb levels. The lymphocyte-monocyte ratio (LMR) was calculated as the

circulating lymphocyte count divided by the circulating monocyte count. The SIS was formulated using dichotomous variables for Alb and LMR. Systemic inflammation-based prognostic scores are shown in Table 1.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA), version 26.0. The normality of distribution for continuous variables was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests. Normally distributed numerical variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation, while non-normally distributed data were presented as median (min–max). Continuous variables were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test, while categorical variables were assessed via the Chi-square or Fisher’s exact analysis. Survival curves were plotted according to the Kaplan-Meier method, and the log-rank test was used to analyze statistical significance. Univariate and multivariate Cox regression analyses were performed when statistically significant differences in survival were identified. The *p*-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Afyonkarahisar Health Science University, Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Board (Date: 06.12.2024; Decision No: 2024/10).

Table1. Systemic inflammation-based prognostic scores.

mGPS	
C-Reactive protein ≤ 10 mg/L and albumin ≥ 35 g/L	0
C-Reactive protein > 10 mg/L	1
C-Reactive protein > 10 mg/L and albumin < 35 g/L	2
SIS	
Lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio ≥ 4.44 and albumin ≥ 40 g/L	0
Lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio < 4.44 and albumin ≥ 40 g/L	1
Lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio ≥ 4.44 and albumin < 40 g/L	1
Lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio < 4.44 and albumin < 40 g/	2
LCS	
Lymphocyte count ≥ 1 × 10 ⁹ /L and C-reactive protein ≤ 3 mg/L	0
Lymphocyte count < 1 × 10 ⁹ /L and C-reactive protein ≤ 3 mg/L	1
Lymphocyte count ≥ 1 × 10 ⁹ /L and C-reactive protein > 3 mg/L	1
Lymphocyte count < 1 × 10 ⁹ /L and C-reactive protein > 3 mg/L	2
mGPS; modified Glasgow Prognostic Score; SIS; systemic inflammation score; LCS; lymphocyte CRP score.	

RESULTS

The mean age of the patients was 60.3 ± 11.7 years. A total of 63 (64.9%) patients were male (Table 2). 56.7% (55 patients) had an ECOG score of 1, and 32% (31 patients) had an ECOG score of 0 (Table 2). 34% (33 patients) had distal tumor localization, and 25.8% (25 patients) had mixed tumor localization. 23 patients (23.7%) had tumors located in the corpus-fundus (Table 2). The majority of patients had no history of gastric surgery (62 patients, 63.9%). Histologically, 77.3% (75 patients) were adenocarcinomas (Table 2). 10 patients (10.3%) were HER2-positive. 81.4% (79 patients)

had metastatic disease at diagnosis (Table 2). Sixteen patients (16.5%) received adjuvant chemotherapy, and four patients (4.1%) received neoadjuvant chemotherapy (Table 2). The most frequent first-line chemotherapy regimens were DCF (docetaxel plus cisplatin plus fluorouracil) at 43.3% and FOLFOX (fluorouracil plus oxaliplatin)/CAPOX (capecitabine plus oxaliplatin) at 35.1% (Table 2). Ten patients (10.3%) received trastuzumab. Partial response to first-line treatment was observed in 56 patients (57.7%), and progression in 31 patients (32%) (Table 2). Only 17.5% of the cases received 3 or more lines of treatment.

Table 2. Demographics and clinical characteristics of 97 GC patients.

Characteristics	Number of patients (%)
Age, mean \pm SD*	60.3 \pm 11.7
Gender,	
Female	34 (35.1)
Male	63 (64.9)
ECOG performance score (PS)	
PS 0	31 (32.0)
PS 1	55 (56.7)
PS 2	9 (9.3)
PS 3	2 (2.1)
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	24.9 \pm 3.9
Localization	
Proximal	16 (16.5)
Corpus-fundus	23 (23.7)
Distal	33 (34.0)
Mixed	25 (25.8)
Type of surgery	
Total gastrectomy	26 (26.8)
Subtotal gastrectomy	9 (9.3)
No surgery	62 (63.9)
Histological type	
Adenocarcinoma	75 (77.3)
Signet ring cell carcinoma	11 (11.3)
Mucinous carcinoma	2 (2.1)
Mixed histology	9 (9.3)
Lauren's classification	
Intestinal	27 (27.8)
Diffuse	33 (34.0)
Mixed	12 (12.4)
Not available	25 (25.8)
Her2 status	
Negative	83 (85.6)
Positive	10 (10.3)
Not available	4 (4.1)
Differentiation status	
Differentiated	50 (51.6)
Undifferentiated	14 (14.4)
Not available	33 (34.0)
TNM stage	
I	1 (1.0)
II	2 (2.1)
III	15 (15.4)
IV	79 (81.4)

Adjuvant chemotherapy	
Absent	2 (2.1)
Present	16 (16.5)
Neoadjuvant chemotherapy	
Absent	14 (14.4)
Present	4 (4.1)
Metastasectomy	
Absent	90 (92.8)
Present	7 (7.2)
First line chemotherapy regimen*	
DCF	42 (43.3)
FOLFOX/CAPOX	34 (35.1)
CF/CX	8 (8.2)
FLOT	4 (4.1)
PACLITAXEL	4 (4.1)
FOLFIRI/IRINOTECAN	3 (3.1)
5-FU/CAPECITABINE	2 (2.1)
Trastuzumab therapy	
Absent	87 (89.7)
Present	10 (10.3)
First line therapy response**	
CR	5 (5.2)
PR	56 (57.7)
SD	5 (5.2)
PD	31 (32.0)
Metastatic therapy line number	
1	46 (47.4)
2	34 (35.1)
≥3	17 (17.5)
CEA (μg/L), mean ± SD	73.0± 379.1
CA 19-9 IU/mL, mean± SD	422.3 ± 1313.5
Albumin g/L, mean ± SD	: docetaxel plus cisplatin plus fluorouracil; FOLFOX/CAPOX: fluorouracil plus oxaliplatin/capecitabine; CF/CX: cisplatin plus fluorouracil/cisplatin plus capecitabine; FLOT: fluorouracil plus oxaliplatin plus docetaxel; FOLFIRI:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DCF: docetaxel plus cisplatin plus fluorouracil; FOLFOX/CAPOX: fluorouracil plus oxaliplatin/capecitabine plus oxaliplatin; CF/CX: cisplatin plus fluorouracil/cisplatin plus capecitabine; FLOT: fluorouracil plus oxaliplatin plus docetaxel; FOLFIRI: fluorouracil plus irinotecan. 	
**CR; complete remission, PR; partial remission, SD; stable disease, PD; progressive disease.	

There were no statistically significant differences in many treatment was significantly higher in the group with a score of clinicopathological features among mGPS scores (Table 3), 1 (p=0.019; Table 4). No statistically significant differences in except that the proportion of male patients was higher in the clinicopathological features were observed across LCS scores mGPS score 1 group (92.3% vs. 7.7%) (Table 3). Among SIS (Table 5). scores, the disease control rate (DCR) in response to first-line

Table 3. Clinicopathological characteristics of GC patients according to mGPS.

	mGPS-0 (N=72)	mGPS-1 (N=13)	mGPS-2 (N=12)	P value
Age, median (range)	62 (31-86)	63 (37-76)	61 (36-77)	0.97
Gender, n (%)				0.049*
Female	27 (37.5)	1 (7.7)	6 (50.0)	
Male	45 (62.5)	12 (92.3)	6 (50.0)	
ECOG performance score (PS) n (%)				0.65
PS 0-1	65 (90.3)	11 (84.6)	10 (83.3)	
PS 2-3	7 (9.7)	2 (15.4)	2 (16.7)	
BMI (kg/m ²), mean ±SD	24.9 ±3.9	25.6 ±4.8	24.4 ±2.8	0.74

Localization, n(%)				0.95
Proximal	12 (16.7)	2 (15.4)	2 (16.7)	
Corpus-fundus	16 (22.2)	4 (30.7)	3 (22.7)	
Distal	26 (36.1)	3 (23.2)	4 (33.3)	
Mixed [†]	17 (25.0)	4 (30.7)	4 (33.3)	
Histological type, n(%)				0.31
Adenocarcinoma	57 (79.2)	8 (61.5)	10 (83.3)	
Others [‡]	15 (20.8)	5 (38.5)	2 (16.7)	
Surgery, n(%)				0.07
Absent	43 (59.7)	12 (92.3)	7 (58.3)	
Present	29 (40.3)	1 (7.7)	5 (41.7)	
Her2 status, n(%)				0.95
Negative	61 (89.7)	11 (84.6)	11 (91.7)	
Positive	7 (10.3)	2 (15.4)	1 (8.3)	
Differentiation status, n(%)				0.63
Differentiated	34 (61.8)	10 (90.9)	6 (75.0)	
Undifferentiated	11 (38.2)	1 (9.1)	2 (25.0)	
First line therapy response, n (%)				0.42
Disease control rate (DCR) [§]	47 (65.3)	11 (84.6)	8 (66.7)	
Progressive disease (PD)	25 (34.7)	2 (15.4)	4 (33.3)	
CEA (µg/L), mean ±SD	92.3 ±440.4	18.1 ±33.2	20.1 ±41.4	0.14
CA 19-9 IU/mL, mean ±SD	502.5 ±1511.4	288.6 ±463.2	99.2 ±259.5	0.31
De-novo metastasis, n(%)				0.08
No	17 (23.6)	0 (0.0)	1 (8.3)	
Yes	55 (76.4)	13 (100)	11 (91.7)	

*Bonferroni method used to calculate the adjusted new p-value, and for all subgroups in the 'Gender' category, p-values were <0.008 and not statistically significant.

† Mixed localization is included, linitis plastica or at least two localizations.

‡ Other histologies include signet ring cell, mucinous, or mixed carcinomas.

§ DCR consists of the sum of complete response (CR), partial response (PR), and stable disease (SD).

Table 4. Clinicopathological characteristics of GC patients according to SIS.

	SIS-0 (N=7)	SIS-1 (N=33)	SIS-2 (N=57)	P value
Age, median (range)	60 (45-66)	62 (31-78)	62 (31-86)	0.55
Gender, n(%)				0.79
Female	2 (28.6)	13 (39.4)	19 (33.3)	
Male	5 (71.4)	20 (59.6)	38 (66.7)	
ECOG performance score (PS) n (%)				0.37
PS 0-1	7 (100)	31 (93.9)	48 (84.2)	
PS 2-3	0 (0.0)	2 (6.1)	9 (15.8)	
BMI (kg/m ²), mean ±SD	23.7 ±1.8	24.9 ±3.7	25.1 ±4.2	0.74
Localization, n(%)				0.60
Proximal	1 (14.3)	5 (15.1)	10 (17.5)	
Corpus-fundus	1 (14.3)	9 (27.3)	14 (24.6)	
Distal	3 (42.8)	13 (39.4)	16 (28.1)	
Mixed [†]	2 (28.6)	6 (18.2)	17 (29.8)	
Histological type, n(%)				0.38
Adenocarcinoma	4 (57.1)	27 (81.8)	44 (77.2)	
Others [‡]	3 (42.9)	6 (18.2)	13 (22.8)	
Surgery, n(%)				0.05
Absent	2 (28.6)	25 (75.8)	35 (61.4)	
Present	5 (71.4)	8 (24.2)	22 (38.6)	
Her2 status, n(%)				0.51
Negative	7 (100)	26 (86.7)	50 (89.3)	
Positive	0 (0.0)	4 (13.3)	6 (10.7)	

Differentiation status, n(%)				0.88
Differentiated	3 (75.0)	14 (73.7)	33 (80.5)	
Undifferentiated	1 (25.0)	5 (26.3)	8 (19.5)	
First line therapy response n (%)				0.019*
Disease control rate (DCR) [§]	3 (42.9)	28 (84.8)	35 (61.4)	
Progressive disease (PD)	4 (57.1)	5 (15.2)	22 (38.6)	
CEA (µg/L), mean ±SD	3.6 ±4.9	161.4 ±632.1	36.2 ±150.5	0.51
CA 19-9 IU/mL, mean ±SD	763.0 ±1100.9	194.3 ±345.2	512 ±1655.9	0.06
De-novo metastasis, n(%)				0.08
No	2 (28.6)	3 (9.1)	13 (22.8)	
Yes	5 (71.4)	30 (90.9)	44 (77.2)	

*Bonferroni method used to calculate the adjusted new p-value, and only for the SIS 1 score, the DCR rate was significantly better in the 'First line therapy response' category (p=0.006 and less than 0.008).

† Mixed localization is included, linitis plastica or at least two localizations.

‡ Other histologies include signet ring cell, mucinous, or mixed carcinomas.

§ DCR consists of the sum of complete response (CR), partial response (PR), and stable disease (SD).

Table 5. Clinicopathological characteristics of GC patients according to LCS.

	LCS-0 (N=36)	LCS-1 (N=52)	LCS-2 (N=9)	P value*
Age, median (range)	61 (31-79)	63.5 (31-86)	65 (44-77)	0.88
Gender, n(%)				0.66
Female	11 (31.6)	19 (36.5)	4 (44.4)	
Male	25 (69.4)	33 (63.5)	5 (55.6)	
ECOG performance score (PS) n (%)				0.06
PS 0-1	35 (97.2)	44 (84.6)	7 (77.8)	
PS 2-3	1 (2.8)	8 (15.4)	2 (22.2)	
BMI (kg/m ²) mean ±SD	25.1 ±3.9	24.9 ±3.4	23.7 ±7.2	0.56
Localization, n(%)				0.60
Proximal	10 (27.8)	4 (7.7)	2 (22.2)	
Corpus-fundus	6 (33.2)	16(30.8)	1 (11.2)	
Distal	14 (38.9)	17 (32.7)	2 (22.2)	
Mixed [†]	6 (33.1)	15 (28.8)	4 (44.4)	
Histological type, n(%)				0.55
Adenocarcinoma	29 (80.6)	38 (73.1)	8 (88.9)	
Others [‡]	7 (19.4)	14 (26.9)	1 (11.1)	
Surgery, n(%)				0.63
Absent	22 (61.1)	35 (67.3)	5 (55.6)	
Present	14 (38.9)	17 (32.7)	4 (44.4)	
Her2 status, n(%)				0.64
Negative	29 (87.9)	46 (90.2)	8 (88.9)	
Positive	4 (12.1)	5 (9.8)	1 (11.1)	
Differentiation status, n(%)				0.38
Differentiated	15 (71.4)	28 (56,0)	7 (14,0)	
Undifferentiated	6 (28.6)	8 (57,1)	0 (0,0)	
First line therapy response n (%)				0.58
Disease control rate (DCR) [§]	26 (39,4)	33 (77.8)	7 (77.8)	
Progressive disease (PD)	10 (32,3)	19 (22.2)	2 (22.2)	

CEA ($\mu\text{g/L}$), mean \pm SD	36.9 \pm 182.3	113.3 \pm 500.4	4.1 \pm 4.5	0.10
CA 19-9 IU/mL	824 \pm 2057.0	196.2 \pm 430.4	143.2 \pm 325.2	0.17
De-novo metastasis n(%)				0.20
No	9 (25.0)	7 (13.5)	2 (22.2)	
Yes	27 (75.0)	45 (86.5)	7 (77.8)	

Mixed lo, linitis plastica, or at least two localizations.
 † Other histologies include signet ring cell, mucinous, or mixed carcinomas.
 § DCR consists of the sum of complete response (CR), partial response (PR), and stable disease (SD).

No significant differences were found between groups in overall progression-free survival for mGPS, SIS, and LCS scores survival for mGPS, SIS, and LCS scores ($p=0.77$, $p=0.14$, $p=0.43$, $p=0.06$, $p=0.97$, respectively, Figure 2). Similarly, no $p=0.21$, respectively, Figure 3).

Figure 2. Kaplan-Meier curves for PFS according to mGPS, SIS, LCS scores groups

Figure 3. Kaplan-Meier curves for OS according to mGPS, SIS, LCS scores groups

When patients were divided into two groups—those who underwent surgery and those who did not—the group without surgery had significantly worse PFS (3.73 months) among patients with an mGPS score of 2 ($p=0.034$; Figure 4). Still, there was no significant difference in overall survival ($p=0.44$, figure 4). Patients with SIS scores of 0 and 1 were grouped (due to the small number of patients in each group) and compared in survival with those with a score of 2. As a result

of these evaluations, in patients without surgery, the SIS score 2 group had a PFS of 5.30 months, while the SIS score 0-1 group had a PFS of 7.34 months, and similarly, the SIS score 2 group had an OS of 13.30 months and the SIS score 0-1 group had an OS of 15.60 months, indicating worse survival times (figure 5). For LCS scoring, there were no significant differences for PFS and OS among patients without surgery ($p=0.93$ and $p=0.97$, respectively).

Figure 4. Kaplan-Meier curves for PFS and OS according to mGPS scores in patients who did not undergo surgery

Figure 5. Kaplan-Meier curves for PFS and OS according to SIS scores in patients who did not undergo surgery

Although no significant survival difference was observed in the surgical group, the sample size was too small to compare scoring systems (n = 35). In the non-surgical group, univariate Cox regression analysis showed that patients with an mGPS score of 1 had a 1.23 times worse PFS than those with an mGPS score of 0 (HR: 1.23, CI: 0.60-2.50, p=0.57, Table 6), and patients with an mGPS score of 2 had a 3.22 times worse PFS than those with an mGPS score of 0 (HR: 3.22, CI: 1.27-8.18, p=0.01, Table 6). A statistically significant decrease in the risk of progression was observed with increasing albumin levels (HR: 0.37, CI: 0.21-0.65, p=0.01; Table 6). As the lymphocyte-monocyte ratio increased, a statistically significant increase in the risk of progression was detected (HR: 1.12, CI: 1.03-3.25, p=0.008, Table 6). Patients with a SIS score of 2 had 1.85 times worse PFS than those with a SIS score of 0-1 (HR: 1.85, CI: 1.05-3.25, p=0.03, Table 6). In the multivariate analysis of PFS, an increase in the lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio was significantly associated with poor PFS (HR: 1.18, CI: 1.08-1.28, p<0.001; Table 6). In the multivariate analysis, higher albumin levels were significantly associated with better PFS (HR: 0.37, CI: 0.15-0.96, p=0.04; Table 6).

Table 6. Cox’s proportional hazard model for PFS in gastric cancer patients who did not undergo surgery

	Univariate analysis		Multivariate analysis	
	p-value	HR (95% CI)	p-value	HR (95% CI)
mGPS (1 vs 0)	0.57	1.23 (0.60-2.50)	0.17	1.72 (0.79-3.74)
mGPS (2 vs 0)	0.01	3.22 (1.27-8.18)	0.33	1.72 (0.58-5.07)
Albumin (continuous variable)	0.01	0.37 (0.21-0.65)	0.04	0.37 (0.15-0.96)
Lymphocyte-monocyte ratio (continuous variable)	0.008	1.12 (1.03-1.22)	<0.001	1.18 (1.08-1.28)
SIS (score 2 vs score 0-1)	0.03	1.85 (1.05-3.25)	0.71	1.19 (0.48-2.98)

In the non-surgical group, Cox regression analyses of overall survival revealed statistically significant associations for albumin and SIS score in the univariate analysis (Table 7). Histologically, patients in the other group had 1.99 times the risk of death compared with those in the adenocarcinoma group, but this was slightly above the statistical significance threshold (HR: 1.99, CI: 0.99-4.00, p=0.052, Table 7). In univariate analysis, a statistically significant improvement in overall survival was observed with increasing albumin (HR: 0.55, CI: 0.34-0.90, p=0.017; Table 7). Patients with a SIS score of 2 had a 2 times higher risk of death compared to those with a score of 0-1 (HR: 2.0, CI: 1.12-3.59, p=0.02, Table 7). In the multivariate model used for overall survival analysis, only histological type was identified as an independent predictor of survival. Patients with other histologies had a 2.49 times worse overall survival than those with adenocarcinoma (HR: 2.49, CI: 1.18-5.27, p=0.017, Table 7).

Table 7. Cox’s proportional hazard model for OS in gastric cancer patients who did not undergo surgery

	Univariate analysis		Multivariate analysis	
	p-value	HR (95% CI)	p-value	HR (95% CI)
Histological type (others vs adenocarcinoma)	0.052	1.99 (0.99-4.00)	0.017	2.49 (1.18-5.27)
Albumin (continuous variable)	0.017	0.55 (0.34-0.90)	0.26	0.63 (0.28-1.42)
SIS (score 2 vs score 0-1)	0.02	2.00 (1.12-3.59)	0.52	1.37 (0.53-3.50)

DISCUSSION

In our study, no statistically significant association between PFS and OS was observed in analyses of the entire cohort across all three scoring systems. However, when stratified by surgery status, patients with an mGPS score of 2 had worse PFS than those with lower scores, and patients with an SIS score of 2 had shorter survival in both PFS and OS among patients who underwent surgery. In multivariate analyses, albumin and the lymphocyte-to-monocyte ratio were independently associated with PFS, whereas for OS, only histological type was independently associated. For LCS scoring, no association with survival was observed, including in the non-surgical patient group.

In their study of 384 patients with advanced gastric cancer receiving first-line chemotherapy, Qing-Qing Li and colleagues found shorter PFS and OS in patients with high mGPS scores ($p=0.002$ and $p=0.006$, respectively).⁵ In our study, although no difference in OS was observed, PFS was significantly shorter (3.73 months) among patients who had not undergone surgery and had an mGPS score of 2. In their study of 402 patients with advanced gastric cancer receiving first-line chemotherapy, Hwang et al. found shorter PFS and OS in patients with high mGPS scores ($p=0.001$ and $p=0.001$, respectively).⁷ In multivariate analysis, they found that patients with mGPS scores of 1 or 2 had a higher risk of having shorter OS compared to those with scores of 0, although not in PFS (HR 1.75 95% CI 1.37-2.26, $P = 0.001$; GPS = 2, HR 1.79, 95% CI 1.29-2.47, $P = 0.001$, respectively).⁷ In their study evaluating 384 gastric cancer patients with peritoneal metastases, Yuan SQ et al. found that patients with mGPS 0 had a longer median OS than those with mGPS 1 or 2 (15.50 months versus 10.07 and 7.97 months, respectively; $p<0.01$).⁸ In the study by Jeong JH et al., an analysis of 104 patients with metastatic gastric cancer who received palliative chemotherapy found that mGPS was an independent prognostic factor for shorter OS ($p=0.01$).⁹

Chen et al. found that the preoperative higher mGPS, SIS, and LCS scores predicted worse OS in GC patients.⁶ In this study, the SIS, comprising preoperative LMR and serum Alb levels, is identified as the most clinically promising and feasible inflammation-based prognostic scoring system.⁶ However, the patient group in that study differed from that in our study. Hirahara N et al. examined 434 patients with resected gastric

cancer. They found that an mGPS score of 2 was associated with significantly worse overall survival and cancer-specific survival than a score of 0 ($p<0.001$ and $p<0.001$, respectively).¹⁰ In this study, no significant difference in survival was observed between individuals with an mGPS score of 1 and those with a score of 0.¹⁰ Melekoğlu E et al. from Turkey evaluated 71 gastric cancer patients over 65 years of age who received perioperative FLOT chemotherapy. They found that a high mGPS score was associated with worse survival in this patient group.¹¹ In the study by Hara K. et al., which included 311 patients, patients with stage 2 and 3 gastric cancer were evaluated, and the 5-year OS rate was 86.6% in the low SIS group and 66.6% in the high SIS group ($p=0.004$).¹² In the same study, relapse-free survival was 79.1% in the low-SIS group and 58% in the high-SIS group ($p=0.07$).¹² In a meta-analysis including 5338 gastric cancer patients who underwent surgery in China and Japan, a high SIS score was found to be significant in predicting poor OS.¹³ In the study, patients with a SIS score of 2 had worse OS than those with a SIS score of 0-1 (HR:2.13, CI: 1.30-4.89).¹³

Regarding inflammatory scoring systems, particularly mGPS, numerous studies exist in both metastatic and earlier-stage patient groups. These studies show poorer survival rates with increasing mGPS score, particularly among patients with a score of 2. For SIS, while some studies show worse survival rates, particularly in patients who have undergone surgery, data are quite limited in metastatic groups. To our knowledge, no studies specifically addressing LCS scoring in gastric cancer have been identified in the literature.

The retrospective nature of our study and the relatively small number of patients (particularly in subgroup analyses) may be considered limitations. However, the scarcity of literature on this topic at the metastatic stage indicates that our study provides important information and that further, larger-scale research is needed in this area.

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